

A NOVEL ANCHOR METHOD OF FRP CABLE FOR LONG-SPAN CABLE-SUPPORTED BRIDGES

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a novel anchor toward large capacity fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) cable with paralleled multi tendons and demonstrates anchor efficiency by the finite element method (FEM) and experiments. The limitations of conventional anchors for FRP cables including the bonding, friction and wedge anchors were first analyzed. Referred to the wedge anchor characteristic using a load transfer component (LTC), a new type of conical anchor with continuous-fiber-reinforced LTC manufactured via molding compression was proposed that addresses both the short- and long-term performance of the anchor. The four key factors of LTC affecting anchor efficiency were analyzed. The experimental demonstration included evaluating the tensile properties of the FRP cable, the strain distribution in the anchor zone and the stress-strain relationship of the cable. The anchor effect was evaluated through a comparison of strain distributions among the FE simulation and experimental results. The results indicate that the winding of fiber roving around each tendon at the anchor zone benefits the integration of the tendons, and the variable elastic modulus of the LTC can be realized through the winding fiber roving with variable angle inclinations and the assistance of compression molding technology. The strain distribution in the anchor zone demonstrates the realization of the variable modulus of the LTC, which benefits smoother and longer shear stress transfer along the longitudinal direction of the anchor zone. The high anchor efficiency of the tested FRP cable demonstrates that the proposed anchor obtains the potential tensile strength of each tendon without any reduction, thus resulting in a high-strength cable.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are widely accepted civil infrastructure reinforcing materials because of their superior physical, mechanical and chemical properties compared with conventional steel reinforcement [1, 2]. Because of the anisotropy property of FRP-pultruded members such as FRP cables, the most efficient way to use FRP is to apply it as a tension-only element using a prestressing technology. Typically prestressed FRP materials include carbon FRP (CFRP) and aramid FRP (AFRP) because of their high strength and high creep rupture stress, typically $0.65 f_u$ and $0.55 f_u$ [3]. In addition to conventional fiber composites, the newly developed basalt fibers produced from volcanic rock have received wide attention recently, and basalt FRP (BFRP) has been gradually applied to structural strengthening because of its integral high performance compared with CFRP and GFRP [4-6], especially its higher tensile strength (approximately 1500 MPa) and higher creep rupture stress ($0.52 f_u$) compared with GFRP tendons [7].

However, the lower transversal strength of FRP cables greatly limits their prestressing applications. Compared with steel cables, the anchors for FRP cables are much more complicated, especially for cables consisting of multi tendons with large diameters. The limitations of the traditional anchorage for FRP cables restrain their application for prestressing, for instance, the potential long-term bonding failure or the significant large creep of the adhesive layer of bonding anchor, the conflict between the necessary anchor length and the practical requirement of friction anchor and the excessive radial stress in wedge anchor.

Thus, this paper proposes a type of new anchor proposed, focusing on its short-term anchor performance. The proposed anchor is optimized through finite element method (FEM) and tensile tests are conducted on the BFRP tendons with the new anchor.

2 ANCHORAGE OPTIMIZATION BY FEM

The anchor components analyzed by ANSYS including the FRP cable, load transfer component (LTC) and steel sleeve were simulated using the PLANE42 element. A group of contact elements (TARGE169 and CONTA171) were adopted to simulate the relative slippage between the sleeve and the LTC. The parameters potentially affecting the properties of the anchor comprise modulus variation of load transfer component, conical degree, anchor length and thickness of LTC at the loading end. Figure 1 shows the analysis results.

Figure 1 Analysis results of FEM

The analysis results show that with the adoption of the variable modulus of LTC, the sudden axial stress drop at the loading end can be greatly relieved. Furthermore, the peak value of the compressive stress shifted from the free end to the middle portion of the LTC and more uniform shear stress can be realized. Modulus values varied from 1 GPa, 5 GPa, 15 GPa to 25 GPa with the ratio of length 1:1.5:6. Conical degrees ranging from 4 to 10 were attempted to determine the optimized degree. The results show that 7 degrees can be a suitable value for LTCs achieving uniform axial stress distribution and acceptable displacement at both ends, as well as satisfactory transversal stress and shear stress distribution. For controlling transversal compressive stress and based on the technical and economic consideration, the anchor length is determined to be 340 mm. A thickness at loading end of

internal conical configuration (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Installation of FRP cable in the reaction frame

The hydro cylinder has a capacity of 1600 kN and a maximum piston stroke of 400 mm. A load cell was connected to the piston and the anchor of the cable to record the loads during the test. The loading rate was 200 MPa/min, and the loading was separated into four stages, with loads maintained at 20, 40 and 60% of the predicted capacity of the FRP cable. The cables were labeled as BC-1, BC-2 and BC-3. All of the strains were recorded using a TDS-530 data logger. Figure 4 shows the loading set-up for FRP cable.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Tensile properties of FRP tendons

All 19 tendons failed at the middle of the specimen by fiber dispersion. The mean strength is 1521 MPa with Coefficient of variation (CV) equal to 4.8% and the mean modulus is 52 MPa with CV equal to 1.8%.

5.2 Results for FRP cable and anchor

5.2.1 Failure mode of the FRP cable and the anchors

All three cables failed at the middle of the cable by the gradual failure of each tendon. When the loading approaches the ultimate load, one of the FRP tendons reaches the failure strain and fractures at the middle portion, after which the load is still maintained and increases continuously. Afterwards, with additional tendon fracture, the load fluctuated and gradually decreased up to the failure of the final tendon of the cable. At the ultimate stage, the load-carrying behavior of the BFRP cable exhibits a gradual failure rather than a rapid and continuous failure of all of the tendons.

The above failure mechanism is also reflected in the load-time relationship of the FRP cables, as shown in Figure 5(a), in which the three platforms represent the load being maintained at 20, 40 and 60% of the predicted capacity of the cable, as discussed above. To show the direct relationship between the load and the time, the platforms were treated as shown in Figure 5(b). After the main tendons fail, the cable force suddenly decreases until the failure of the last tendon.

(a) Original curves with load maintaining platform (b) Treated curves
Figure 5 Load-time curves for three FRP cables

The failure modes of the LTC are shown in Figure 6. Note that after the fracture of the entire cable, no failure or slippage of the FRP tendons in the LTC can be observed from either the free end or the loading end (Figure 6(a-b)). Images of the LTC cross-sections that were cut from the free end, middle portion and loading end of the LTC are shown in Figure 6(c-e), which also display the perfect bond between each tendon and the tendons with the LTC.

(a) Free end (b) Loading end

(c) Nearby free end (d) Middle portion (e) Nearby loading end

Figure 6 Failure modes of LTC

5.2.2 Strain development in FRP cables and the anchor zone

(1) Axial strain in the middle portion of the FRP cable

The linear relationships between strains and loads of BC-1 are shown in Figure 7, which shows that the majority of the tendons exhibit similar strain development with respect to the load. The curves for BC-2 and BC-3 behave similar with that for BC-1. Furthermore, the BC-3 cable exhibits the highest capacity among the three cables, because the ultimate capacity of the cable is primarily determined by the least-deformed tendon in the cable.

Figure 7 Strain-Load relationship of BC-1

(2) Evaluation of strain distribution in the anchor zone in comparison with FE simulation

The cable strains at the different positions of the anchor zone are further compared with the results of the FE simulation, as shown in Figure 8. When comparing the experimental and FE results, we observe that with increasing load, the experimental strain distribution gradually approaches the curve of the FE variable modulus and almost overlaps them under the ultimate load. This phenomenon indicates that the tested anchor exhibits a variable modulus of the LTC and the simultaneous work of the LTC in the tested anchor varies depending on the load amplitude. Furthermore, note that under high load levels, the approaching curves between the experimental and FE variable modulus demonstrate the superior anchor effects.

(a) At first platform (20% f_u)

(b) At second platform (40% f_u)

(c) At third platform (60% f_u) (d) At ultimate stage (f_u)
Figure 8 Comparison of strain distribution among experiment and FE simulation

5.2.3 Anchor efficiency

The fundamental criterion used to evaluate the performance of the anchor is the coefficient of anchor efficiency, which is obtained by the following equation (PTI 1997):

$$\eta_a = \frac{F_{apu}}{F_{pm}} = \frac{F_{apu}}{f_s A_f N_f} \quad (1)$$

where F_{apu} is the tensile capacity of the FRP cable and F_{pm} is the standard value of the tensile strength of the FRP tendon (f_s) multiplied by the number of tendons (N_f) and the cross-sectional area of tendon (A_f). Here, to ensure a reliability of 95%, the standard value of the tensile strength of the FRP tendon can be obtained by $f_s = f_{avg} (1-1.645CV)$. f_{avg} is the mean value of the tensile strength. The calculated anchor efficiency coefficients of the three tested cables are listed in Table 1.

The mean value of the anchor efficiency coefficient is greater than 100% and that even the minimum value of BC-1 is 99.7%. The above data demonstrate that the newly proposed anchor for the BFRP cable consisting of 19 tendons can achieve equivalent or better performance compared to the bonding anchor of a single tendon.

Table 1 Coefficient of anchor efficiency

Specimen	F_{apu} (kN)	$f_{apu}(MPa)^*$	F_{pm} (kN)	$f_s(MPa)$	η_a
BC-1	332	1391	333	1396	99.7%
BC-2	336	1408	333	1396	101%
BC-3	345	1446	333	1396	104%
Mean	338	1416	333	1396	102%
SD	6.66	28.16			2.00%
CV	1.97%	1.99%			1.97%

* f_{apu} represents the experimental tensile strength of cable

Based on the above analysis of the strain distribution in the anchor zone and the evaluation of the anchor efficiency coefficient, we conclude that the proposed anchor for a multi-tendon FRP cable can achieve high static performance through a set of optimal design and manufacturing technologies of the LTC and integration of the cable.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study proposed a novel anchor method for FRP cable. The anchor method was optimized by FE analysis, based on which, the FRP cables with the anchor method were manufactured and tensile

tests were conducted on them. The major conclusions are drawn as follows:

(1) Based on the analyses of axial stress and displacement, transversal compressive stress and interfacial shear stress of the LTC, an optimized LTC consisting of the four portions modulus variation, a conical shape of 7 degrees, an anchor length of 340 mm and an LTC thickness of 15 mm at the loading end was determined.

(2) The failure mode of the LTC and axial strain distribution comparison along the anchor zone between the experiments and FE simulation demonstrated that the proposed anchor concept is realized through the special manufacturing process.

(3) The new anchor achieves a high anchor efficiency, which demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed anchor for the FRP cable with multiple tendons.

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REFERENCES

- [1] L.C. Hollaway. A review of the present and future utilisation of FRP composites in the civil infrastructure with reference to their important in-service properties. *Construction and Building Materials*, 24, 2010, pp. 2419–2445.
- [2] C. Bakis, L. Bank, V. Brown, E. Cosenza, J. Davalos, J. Lesko, A. Machida, S. Rizkalla, and T. Triantafillou. Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Composites for Construction—State-of-the-Art Review, *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 6(2), 2002, pp. 73–87.
- [3] ACI 440.4R-04. Prestressing Concrete Structures with FRP Tendons, American Concrete Institute, 2004.
- [4] J. Sim, C. Park, D.Y. Moon. Characteristics of basalt fiber as a strengthening material for concrete structures, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 36 (6-7), 2005, pp. 504-512.
- [5] Z. Wu, X. Wang, G. Wu. Advancement of Structural Safety and Sustainability with Basalt Fiber Reinforced Polymers, *the sixth International Conference on FRP Composites in Civil Engineering (CICE2012)*, July 22-24, 2012, Rome, Italy.
- [6] X. Wang, Z. Wu, G. Wu, et al. Enhancement of basalt FRP by hybridization for long-span cable-stayed bridge, *Composites Part B: Engineering (Elsevier)*, 44(1), 2013, pp. 184-192.
- [7] X. Wang, J. Shi, J. Liu, L. Yang, and Z. Wu. Creep Behavior of Basalt Fiber Reinforced Polymer Tendons for Prestressing Application, *Journal of Materials and Design*, 59, 2014, pp. 558-564.